

Original Article

Frequency of Normal Low Density Lipoprotein Level in Patients Presenting with Stroke

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ABSTRACT

Background: Stroke remains a major cause of death, and the main cause of severe disability. Various risk factors for stroke including LDL level. The paradox of a high stroke incidence in populations with low serum cholesterol has been reported in population-based studies. But not much work has been done in this regard. Moreover, there is no local study found in literature. So, we conducted this study. The objective of this study was to assess the frequency of normal LDL level in patients presenting with stroke. **Methodology:** A cross sectional study was conducted in the Department of Medicine, Services Hospital, Lahore for the six months from June to December 2018. A total of 385 cases were included in study from emergency after written consent and blood sample were obtained in a 3cc syringe. All samples were sent to the laboratory of the hospital for assessment of LDL level. Reports were assessed and normal LDL level was labelled if level was in normal range. All the information was collected on proforma. All the collected data was entered and analysed into SPSS version 21. **Results:** The patients mean age was 51.87 ± 10.19 years. There were 247 (64.2%) males and 138 (35.8%) females. The mean BMI of patients was $28.95 \pm 6.71 \text{ kg/m}^2$. There were 65 (16.9%) patients who had haemorrhagic stroke while 320 (83.1%) patients had ischemic stroke. History of smoking was positive in 108 (28.1%) cases. Whereas diabetes was positive in 127 (33.0%) cases. The mean serum LDL level of patients was $3.63 \pm 0.82 \text{ mmol/L}$. There were 173 (44.9%) patients with normal LDL level while among 212 (55.1%) patients, LDL level was high. **Conclusion:** The frequency of normal LDL level is almost as equal as deranged LDL level in patients of stroke and patients of ischemic stroke have less chances of normal LDL level than those with haemorrhagic stroke patients.

Key words: Normal LDL level, low density lipoprotein, stroke, ischemic, haemorrhagic

Introduction

Stroke remains a major cause of death, and the main cause of severe disability, in the United States, it is particularly prevalent among elderly individuals,

minorities, and those of lower socioeconomic status.¹ According to World Health Organization (WHO) estimates, 5.5 million people died of stroke in 2002, & roughly 20% of these deaths occurred in South Asia. No large scale epidemiological

research is available to determine the incidence of stroke in Pakistan. Annual incidence is estimated to be 250/100,000, which translates to 350,000 new cases each year.^{2,3}

Stroke is caused by the disruption of the blood supply to the brain, which cuts off the supply of nutrients & oxygen, causing damage or ischemia to the brain issues.^{4,5} The most typical symptom of a stroke is abrupt weakness or numbness on one side of the body, which is known as a focal neurological impairment.⁶

In 2013, approximately 6.9 million people had an ischemic stroke & 3.4 million people had a hemorrhagic stroke.⁷ In 2015 there were about 42.4 million people who had previously a stroke and were still alive.

Various risk factors for stroke include diabetes mellitus, ischemic heart disease, hypertension and also LDL.⁸ Cholesterol levels are inconsistently associated with the risk of stroke.⁹ The most important modifiable risk factors for stroke are high blood pressure and atrial fibrillation although the size of the effect is small with 833 people have to be treated for 1 year to prevent one stroke.^{10,11} Other modifiable risk factors include high blood cholesterol levels, cigarette smoking, diabetes mellitus^{12,13} heavy alcohol use,^{14,15} uses of drug,¹⁶ lack of physical activity, obesity, processed red meat consumption,¹⁷ and unhealthy diet. Even smoking one cigarette a day increases the risk by more than 30%.¹⁸

Low-density lipoprotein (LDL) is one of the five major groups of lipoprotein which transport all fat molecules around the body in the extracellular water.⁽¹⁹⁾ These groups, from least dense, compared to surrounding water (largest particles) to most dense (smallest particles), are chylomicrons, very low-density lipoprotein (VLDL), intermediate-density lipoprotein (IDL), low-density lipoprotein and HDL. LDL delivers fat molecules to the cells and can drive the progression

of atherosclerosis if they become oxidized within the walls of arteries.

The rationale of this study is to assess the frequency of normal LDL level in patients presenting with stroke. Literature showed that the frequency of normal LDL was high and is present in almost in half of the patients. But not much work has been done in this regard. Moreover, there is no local study found in literature which could help us in determining the extent of problem in local population. So, the present study was conducted so that we can attain local magnitude and we can plan screening of stroke patients for lipid profile, especially LDL levels to update the management protocols for such cases.

Methodology

This was a cross-sectional descriptive study, This descriptive cross sectional study was conducted from June to December 2018 in the Department of Medicine, Services Hospital Lahore. After obtaining permission from the Institutional Review Board of the hospital, patients gave their informed written consent. Sample size was calculated to be 385 with 80% power of test and 5% level of significance by taking expected percentage of normal LDL level i.e., 50.1% patients presenting with stroke.

Demographic information (including name, age, gender, BMI, type of stroke, history of smoking (>5 pack year), diabetes [BSR>186mg/dl]) were also recorded. Then patients were admitted as per hospital protocol and blood sample was obtained in a 3cc syringe. All samples were sent to the laboratory of the hospital for the assessment of LDL level. Reports were assessed and normal LDL level was labelled if level was in normal range. All the information was collected on a specially designed proforma.

Data was entered in SPSS 21 value of BMI and LDL were presented as mean \pm standard deviation. Qualitative variables like gender, type of stroke,

smoking, diabetes and normal LDL level were presented as frequency and percentage. Data was stratified for age, gender, smoking, BMI, diabetes & type of stroke to control effect modifiers. Post-stratification, chi-square test was applied to compare the frequency of normal LDL level in stratified groups. P-value ≤ 0.05 was taken as statistically significant.

Results

In our study, there were total 385 patients including 247 (64.2%) males and 138 (35.8%) females. The mean ages and BMI of patients was 51.87±10.19years and 28.95±6.71kg/m². There were 180 (46.7%) patients in 35-50 years of age and 205 (53.2%) were in between the age of 51-70 years (Table-1).

Table-1: Descriptive statistics of age, BMI, LDL & gender.

	Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum- maximum
Age in years	51.87	10.19	35-70
BMI (kg/m²)	28.95	6.71	16.78-40.08
LDL (mmol/L)	3.63	0.82	2.51-5.00
Gender	Male	Female	
	247 (64.2%)	138 (35.8%)	

Data was stratified for gender of patients. In males, 110 (44.5%) patients had with normal LDL level. In females, 63 (45.7%) patients were with normal LDL level. There was insignificant difference (p>0.05) between these variables. Data was stratified for age, BMI, stroke, smoking and diabetes of patients. In patients aged 35-50 years, 80 (44.4%) patients with normal LDL level. In patients aged 51-70 years, 93 (45.4%) patients with normal LDL level. The difference was insignificant (p>0.05) as shown in Table-2. There were 16 (55.2%) underweight patients, patient with normal BMI 41(43.2%), 46 (50%) overweight patients were with normal LDL level. In obese patients, 35 (47.3%) patients were

with normal LDL level. In morbidly obese patients, 35 (36.8%) patients were with normal LDL level. The difference was insignificant (p>0.05). Data was stratified for type of stroke shown in Table-2. In patients with haemorrhagic stroke, 38 (58.5%) and ischemic stroke 135 (42.2%) patients with normal LDL level. The difference was significant (p<0.05). In smokers, 49 (45.4%) whereas in non-smokes 124 (44.8%) patients had with normal LDL level. The difference was insignificant (p>0.05). In diabetics, 69 (54.3%) patients with normal LDL level. In non-diabetics, 104 (40.3%) patients with normal LDL level. The difference was significant (p<0.05) as shown in Table-2.

Table-2: Comparison of normal LDL level with gender, age, BMI, stroke, smoking and diabetes strata.

		Normal LDL		P value
		Yes	No	
Gender	Male	110(44.5%)	137(55.5%)	0.833
	Female	63(45.7%)	75(54.3%)	

Age (years)	31-35 years	80(44.4%)	100(55.6%)	0.856
	51-70	93(45.5%)	112(54.6%)	
BMI	Underweight	26(55.2%)	13(44.8%)	0.28
	Normal	41(43.2%)	54(56.8%)	
	Overweight	46(50%)	46(50%)	
	Obese	35(47.3%)	39(52.7%)	
	Morbidity Obese	35(36.8%)	60(63.2%)	
Stroke	Hemorrhagic	38(58.5%)	27(41.5%)	0.016
	Ischemic	135(42.2%)	185(57.8%)	
Smoking	Yes	49(45.4%)	59(54.6%)	0.91
	No	124(44.8%)	153(55.2%)	
Diabetes	Yes	69(54.3%)	104(40.3%)	0.009
	No	58(45.7%)	154(59.7%)	

Discussion

The paradox of a high stroke incidence in people with low serum cholesterol has been reported in population-based studies.

The paradox of a high stroke rate among patients with low serum cholesterol has been found through population-based studies. An inverse relation between hemorrhagic stroke & serum cholesterol is one possible reason for this finding. Haemorrhagic stroke accounts for up to 30% of all strokes in Asian societies with low plasma cholesterol levels.²⁰

While other factors are likely to play a role in the high prevalence of intra-cerebral haemorrhage in these nations, low cholesterol levels have been suggested as one explanation for the high rate of intra-cerebral haemorrhage. Hemorrhagic stroke was observed in 32% of cases in a population-based study from North-East India.²¹

In our study, the mean age of patients was 51.87 ± 10.19 years. There were 247 (64.2%) males and 138 (35.8%) females. The mean BMI of patients was 28.95 ± 6.71 kg/m². The mean serum LDL level of patients was 3.63 ± 0.82 mmol/L. There

were 173 (44.9%) patients with normal LDL level while among 212 (55.1%) patients, LDL level was high (Results are repeated).

It has been reported that the normal LDL level was present in 50.1% patients presenting with stroke.²² Another study also showed that there were 27% whose measured LDL was high while 73% had normal LDL level.²³ No local study²⁴ showed that the mean LDL level ranged in normal level in patients of stroke i.e., 98.65 ± 33.65 mg/dl.²⁵

Corroborating previous findings examining intracerebral hemorrhage and cholesterol, a moderate inverse association between LDL & intracerebral haemorrhage has been observed.²⁶ Data was stratified for type of stroke. In patients with haemorrhagic stroke, 38 (58.5%) patients were with normal LDL level. In patients with ischemic stroke, 135 (42.2%) patients were with normal LDL level. The difference was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). It can be proposed that the deranged level of LDL can be a factor for ischemic stroke than haemorrhagic stroke.

Khan et al., conducted a study in Pakistan, found that ischemic stroke patients had significantly higher frequency of hypercholesterolemia than

patients of hemorrhagic stroke. Screening dyslipidemia for high risk patients for stroke & lipid lowering therapy are recommended as preventive measures.²⁷

In contrast, a large cohort study of over 14,000 middle aged men and women found no consistent association between LDL-C and ischemic stroke during 10 years of follow-up.²⁸

Conclusion

The frequency of normal LDL level is almost as equal as deranged LDL level in patients of stroke and patient of ischemic stroke have less chances of normal LDL level than haemorrhagic stroke patients. Now we have got the local evidence and we will now implement the results in local setting. Also, we will screen the patients of stroke for lipid profile, especially LDL levels to update the management protocols for such cases.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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Contributions of the Authors

SA, AH, IA devised the plan
IA, AF, HH wrote the manuscript
AM did overall supervision
AM,AH repharsed and did statistical anayeses

